

Emotiology-emotions Linguistics

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Emotions The linguist appears at the crossroads of psychology and linguistics, and became many prominent linguistics (N.A. Krasavsky¹, E.Myagkova², V.I Shakhovsky³). At the end of the twentieth century V.I. Shahovsky introduced the term "emotional" to linguistics. This direction studies the place of emotions in human activity. According to Shahovsky, "With the idea of human emotional condition, we can tell you clearly that we know who he is. During the communications process, emotional reactions show human values and goals. Understanding emotions is the key to understanding the personality of the human personality. The introduction of this term not only allowed our feelings and emotional state, but also to determine the level of description of the interviewee reflectation.

Emotions, mental circumstances are reflected in human thinking and language. Emotional situations reflected in the language have their own characteristics. The feelings serve as a motive (goal) in the process of man knowing, determines the internal world. In the perception of the external world, the inner world is of great importance. "The feelings are not only a form of emergence of reality in the domestic world, but emotion is a means of expressing the person's attitude."⁴

Western linguists have been focusing on linguist linguistics, but also in Uzbek linguistics have been focused on the research on emotiology before this period. It is so pleased that Uzbek linguistics had been introduced into several scientific research work to the Committee of the Science and that emotions linguistics in these cases.

According to researcher G.M Nosirova, emotions are not only of the psyche of a person, but also of the mind. The attitude of mind and spirituality is very

¹ Красавский Н. А. Эмоциональный концепт "отвращение" в романе Роберта Музиля "душевные смуты воспитанника тёрлеса".// Филологические науки. Вопросы теории и практики (входит в перечень ВАК), 2015.114-118. Красавский Н. А. Эмоциональные концепты в немецкой и русской лингвокультурах: монография. Волгоград: Перемена, 2001. 495 с.

² Мягкова Э.Ю. Язык – эмоции – сознание – культура в теории а. дамасио., Тверь, Россия; 2022. 72-85 с.

³ В. И. Шаховский Язык и эмоции в аспекте лингвокультурологии. Волгоград Издательство ВГПУ «Перемена» 2009.

⁴ В. И. Шаховский Язык и эмоции в аспекте лингвокультурологии. Волгоград Издательство ВГПУ «Перемена» 2009. 78с

complicated, and how psychologists have the problems on how one of the leadership of one. The tradition of assessing human conscious feelings as a lower stage (nizki uroven) is much common: "In the first place, it is impossible to target and assess its results."⁵

The problem of studying emotional components expressed in man and its language, the emotional components has emerged from the distinctive discussions of philosophers and psychologists about specifications between emotions and contemplation. In linguistics, the problem reflected in the discussions that scientists should be at the center of Linguistical Studies, associated with the fundamental-cognitive or emotional function of the language. Since then, the language also serves to deliver information, but also to express the internal emotional world. He has attracted scientists to the scholars of interest to the emotional contribution. The emotions were originally objects of study: Philosophy, psychology, linguistics, as a result of which emotional associations, community with biologists, physiologists, and other professionals Ko " The RIB has begun. In the interpersonal dialogue, the role of emotions in human life is incomparable. The emotional side of human life is inextricably linked with activities in all forms. The feelings represent the attitude of a person to the surrounding reality events. The human emotional system is one of the most complex systems, including a multifaceted, including linguistic research. Today, the study of emotions is one of the urgent tasks in this area. Such feelings are explained by the fact that today is covering the entire communicative space: including these include: politics, journalism, public, daily and artistic communication. The feelings have become the most important components of modern human thinking and linguistic consciousness. For linguistics, the problem of semantically interpreting and consistently recognized as the most important aspect of semantically interpreting emotions. Feelings are one of the forms of reflecting reality, which are an integral part of human existence and plays an important role in human life. In the process of understanding reality, things and events, we react to them, show our attitude in different forms, feelings, which is undoubtedly reflected in the language. In this way, we can see even more brighter that feelings are that man is a complex product of the spiritual and cognitive activities of man. The study of their language methods is especially important to explain the linguing of the learning.

⁵ Общая психология. Москва. Просвещения, 1986 – С.28.

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